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MUNDARIJA

ПРИНЦИПЫ ПЕРЕХОДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ, СУЩЕСТВУЮЩИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВНЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ	12
Набиев Дилмурод Хамидуллаевич	
YaShIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLASH TIRISH TA'SIRIDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TRANSFORMASIYASI	19
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xo'jaevich	
РОЛЬ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ТРУДА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЕГО ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ	26
Гулямов Саидахор Саидахмедович, Икрамов Мурат Акрамович, Очилов Акрам Одилович	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASH MAQSADIDA "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT"GA O'TISH ZARURATI	33
O.X. Hamidov, D.Sh. Yavmutov	
ESG-ИНСТРУМЕНТАРИЙ КАК ФАКТОР УСИЛЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	38
Татьяна Юрьевна Анопоченко, Сергей Вадимович Ревунов, Роман Вадимович Ревунов	
TRANSITION OF RUSSIAN REGIONS TO A CLOSED-LOOP ECONOMY	49
Nikonov Sergey Mikhailovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Filipenko Alexander Alexandrovich	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNING MOHIYATI VA TUZILISHI	53
Navruz-Zoda Baxtiyor Negmatovich	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК ДРАЙВЕР УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА И МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ РАБОЧИХ МЕСТ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	59
Зокирова Нодира Каландаровна	
KREATIV IQTISODIYOT VA UNING INDUSTRIYA TURLARINING NAZARIY MASALALARI	64
Mamayunus Pardaev, Obid Pardaev, Akram Ochilov	
EKOLOGIK OMILLARNI HISOBGA OLGAN HOLDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHDA ERISHISH	73
Saidov Muhammadali Hakimovich, Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Esanbekov Diyorbek Mirzabek o'g'li	
INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOTCHILIK MAHSULOTLARI KOOPERASIYASINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	81
Rahmatulla Ergashev	
KARTOSHKA MOSLANUVCHAN NAVLARI TURLI EKISH MUDDATLARI VA MULCHALASHLARDA HOSILDORLIGI HAMDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI	86
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Toshpulatova Surayyo Tulqin qizi, Ismayilov Alisher Isroilovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHNING KALITI	90
Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanakovich, Usmonov Murodjon Dusmurot o'g'li	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ» В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	93
Сайёра Насимовна Хамраева	
SABZAVOT (SHIRIN) MAKKAJO'XORI AJRATILGAN MOSLANUVCHAN NAV-DURAGAYLARINI ASOSIY VA TAKRORIY EKINLAR SIFATIDA TURLI MUDDATLARDA YETISHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	97
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Nurillaev Ilhom Xolbek o'g'li, Jabborov Botir Shukurovich	
ZAMONAVIY BOZOR MUNOSABATLARIDA SAVDONI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY VA USLUBIY JIHATLARI	101
Ivatov Irisbek	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	105
Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich, Abdiyeva Flora Botir qizi	
GREEN ECONOMY: GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE AND UZBEKISTAN'S PATH	110
Dilmurod Mirza-Akhmedovich Rasulev, Dildorakhon Ulugbek kizi Shomuradova	

OLIV TA'LIM XIZMATLARINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TARG'IB QILISH BO'YICHA XORIJ TAJRIBASI	113
Musayev Bekjon Shukurillayevich	
TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINI BARQAROR STRATEGIK RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN USULLAR TAHLILI	116
Turdibekov Xasan Ibragimovich	
ЗЕЛЁНОЕ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЕ И ФАКТОРЫ ЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	120
Орипов Ильхом Абдуллаевич	
Перспективы развития цифровой трансформации в Республике Узбекистан	128
Мусабеков Джорабек Хакимджанович, Воронин Сергей Александрович	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNING MUHIM OMILI SIFATIDA.....	133
G.Erkayeva	
Barqaror ish o'rinlarini yaratishda yashil iqtisodiyotning o'rni	138
Qo'chqorov G'aybulla Fayzullayevich, Qo'ziyeva Shaxnoza Bozor qizi	
ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	141
Фазлитдин Бахадирович Аминов	
RESPUBLIKADA EKOLOGIK TOZA MAHSULOT YETISHTIRISH ASOSIDA ELEKTRON SAVDONI RIVOJLANTIRISH	145
Q. J. Mirzayev, F. F. Ulug'murodov	
Qoraqalpog'istonda sanoatni restruktizatsiyalash va yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish: muammolar, istiqbollar va statistik tahlillar	150
Abipova Gulmira Salavatdinovna	
CHORVACHILIK XO'JALIKLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AGLOMERATSIYANING AHAMIYATI.....	153
Xusainov Oybek Jabborovich	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA STRATEGIYASINING KOMPANIYA UCHUN AHAMIYATI.....	156
Ergashev Toxir Kurbanovich, Toxirova Nigora Zokirjon qizi	
CHORVACHILIK KLASSTERLARI VA AGLOMERATSION RIVOJLANISH: O'ZARO TA'SIR VA SYNERGIYALAR	161
Xusainov Oybek Jabborovich	
HUDUDLARNING INNOVATSIYON SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASH	165
J.A. Ismatullayev, A. Do'lanov	
СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	171
Нафасов Тохиржон, Г. П. Эркаева	
Mamlakatimizda ishsizlikni kamaytirishga qaratilgan islohotlar.....	174
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich	
USE OF THE ADVANCED EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES OF FARMING AND HOUSEHOLDS	178
Ochilova Nargiza Akramovna	
SHAHAR AGLOMERATSIYALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI.....	181
Xidayatova Nigora Shorakibovna	
IQTISODIY O'SISHDA MEHNAT MIGRATSIYASINING AHAMIYATI.....	184
Djurayev Olimjon Narkulovich, Saidakbarov Jamshid Ne'matullo o'g'li	
TURIZMNIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TRANSPORT XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	189
Qosimov Jahongir 189	
РЫНОК ГОСТИНИЧНЫХ УСЛУГ В ТУРИЗМЕ В УСЛОВИЯХ ДИВЕРСИФИКАЦИИ И ДЕМОКРАТИЗАЦИИ ГОСТИНИЧНОЙ ИНДУСТРИИ	192
Ташмаматов Садирдин Нажмиддинович	

O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASIDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KADRLAR MALAKASINI OSHIRISHDA DUAL TA'LIMDAN FOYDALANISHNI BOSHQARISH.....	196
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Xamidova Mo'tabarxon Abdumalik qizi	
MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA AUTSORSING XIZMATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	201
Nasiba Ergasheva	
KORXONALARDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISHNING ASOSIY TAMOYILLARI	207
Djuraev Olimjon Narkulovich, Nurullayeva Vazira O'ktamovna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИИ: ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ И РИСКИ	211
Номазов Бахром Бобомуродович	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ПРИНЦИПОВ ESG В ФИНАНСОВУЮ СФЕРУ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	215
Алимова Азиза Шерзатовна	
THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES ON MANAGEMENT	219
Ergashev Tokhir Kurbanovich, Tohirova Nigora Zokirjon kizi	
O'ZBEKISTONNING "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT STRATEGIYASI" NI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING ZARURIYATI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	224
Ergasheva Nazira Muratovna, Soyibov Mirjon Bekjonovich	
ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ УСЛУГ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИХ НА ПОВЫШЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ И КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ	227
Алимова Муниса Юлчиевна	
РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОБУВНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЕЁ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЗНАЧИМОСТИ.....	232
Расулов Нозимжон Набиджонович	
AGLOMERATSIYA VA IQTISODIY O'SISH: SABAB-OQIBAT ALOQASI (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	236
Xidoyatova Nigora Shorakibovna	
KORXONALARNING SOLIQ IDORALARIDA HISOBGA OLINISHIDAN HOSIL BO'LGAN ORTIQCHA TO'LOVLARINI BOJXONA TO'LOVLARIDA HISOBGA OLISH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	239
Boykabilov Bahodir Mustafaevich	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLARGA INVESTITSIYALAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	242
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
ORGANIK QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA "IXTISOSLASHTIRILGAN AGROKOOPERATIV" TASHKIL ETISH ORQALI TA'MINOT ZANJIRI BOSHQARUVINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	248
Amirqulov Shuxrat Olimovich	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING MOLIVAVIY RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHI UCHUN ZAMONAVIY HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	254
Xayriddinov Shuxrat Botirovich	
TURIZMNING MADANIY-TARIXIY RESURSLARI: ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALAR VA TAMOYILLAR	258
Ruzmanov Dilshod Usmanovich	
BARQAROR TURIZM DESTINATSIYALARINING SIG'IMINI VAHOLASH METODIKASI.....	262
Ibroximov Nodirbek Xasanovich	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫЕ ИСТОЧНИКИ ЭНЕРГИИ КАК ОСНОВА ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНА	266
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ МАРКЕТИНГ И ПОВЕДЕНИЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЕЙ.....	272
Раимова Муборак Джураевна	
"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" NING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI	276
Djumayev Asqar Xaydarovich	

RAQAMLI MARKETINGNING ISTE'MOLCHI XULQ-ATVORIGA TA'SIRI.....	281
Raimova Muborak Jurayevna, Dilmurodov O'tkir	
HUDUDNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI	287
SH.A. Buriyev	
SAVDO XIZMATLARINING ASOSIY FAOLIYAT KO'RSATKICHLARI TIZIMINI BAHOLASH.....	291
Muxamedova Aziza Ravshanovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA GLOBAL IQLIM O'ZGARISHI: YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING IQLIM O'ZGARISHINI YENGISHDAGI O'RNI VA GLOBAL HAMKORLIK.....	295
Usmonov Murodjon Xolmurod o'g'li, Ulug'bek Eshmaxmatov	
КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ МЕХАНИЗМА НАЛОГОВОГО АДМИНИСТРИРОВАНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	299
Абдулов Дамир Рустамович	
О'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH ISTIQBOLLARI	305
Yuldashev Shamsiddin Qiyamiddinovich, Boliyeva Baxora Farxodovna	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА: КОНЦЕПЦИИ, ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ.....	308
Туляганова Шахноза Самукджановна	
О'ТА ERTAGI TARVUZNING HIMOYALANGAN JOYLAR UCHUN MOSLANUVCHAN NAV VA DURAGAYLARINI AJRATISH, ULARNI TURLI O'G'IT ME'YORLARIDA HOSILDORLIGI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	311
Ostonaqulov Toshtemir Eshimovich, Amirov Xamidulla Suyunovich, Umirova Durdona Muqum qizi	
ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ПЛОДООВОЩНОЙ ОТРАСЛИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	315
Уралов Элшод, Вельм М.В.	
DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY AS A MODEL OF PROGRESS IN HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	320
Abdiev Alimardon	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СЕКТОРА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ СЛУЖБЫ И РАЗВИТИЯ КАДРОВОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА.....	322
Мухаммадбобур Салимов	
КИЧИК BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR.....	326
Suyunov Jabbor Mahmudovich	
“SALOHİYAT” TUSHUNCHASINING MAZMUNI VA IQTISODIY-IJTIMOIIY MOHIYATI.....	331
Zoirov G'olibjon Toshtemir o'g'li	
DAVLAT BOSHQARUVIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKTDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI	334
Salimov Muhammadbobur Qodir o'g'li	
O'QUV JARAYONLARINI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	337
Tilakov Sherzod	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING XALQARO TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING AHAMIYATI.....	340
Sattarov Umirzoq, Ro'ziev Zafar Ikromovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT XOM ASHYOLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	343
Xazratov Sarvar Ibragimovich	
YURTIMIZDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASHNING ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	348
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, O'rinov Diyorbek Xolmo'min o'g'li	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI O'QUV MARKAZLARI VA KURSLARINI BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	353
Tilakov Sherzod Akbarovich	

SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MAHSULOT ISHLAB CHIQRARISH VA SOTISH SIFATI HAMDA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	357
Ochilov Akram Odilovich, Ziyodullayeva Marjona Alisher qizi	
OMMAVIY TADBIRLAR YORDAMIDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: O'ZBEKISTON VA XALQARO TAJRIBA.....	360
Ibragimov Sardorbek Xusanovich	
Анализ цифровой трансформации и её влияния на привлечение инвестиций в регионы Узбекистана.....	365
Рахмонова Дурдона Хасан кизи	
Korxonada moliyaviy salohiyatini baholashning statistik tahlili.....	370
M.O. Musurmonova	
DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF THE BANKING SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Kadirov Lutfulla Khalimovich	
PROBLEMS OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE LABOR MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR THEIR SOLUTION.....	381
Sharopov Temirmalik Rustam o'g'li	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ORQALI QASHQADARYO VILOYATI SANOAT KOMPLEKSINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	385
U.Shukurov	
FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN SERVICE INDUSTRIES	390
Hazratkulov Shahboz Boboqul ogli	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA TA'LIMNING ROLI.....	394
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISHI UCHUN DAVLAT TOMONIDAN YARATILAYOTGAN IMKONIYATLAR.....	398
Xudoyorov Azizbek Avaz o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA TA'LIM SIFATINI YAXSHILASHNING XORIY TAJRIBASI.....	404
Safarov Sh. S.	
IJTIMOYIY MENEJMENTDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	408
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, Davronova Farangiz	
«ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ ФИНАНСОВЫЙ КОНТРОЛЬ: КАЗНАЧЕЙСКИЙ КОНТРОЛЬ В БЮДЖЕТНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ»	415
Файзуллаева Зилола Равшановна, Д.Х. Пулатов	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING ASOSIY JIHATLARI.....	421
Urozoza Shaxlo Hasan qizi, Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI	427
Safarov Shoxrux Sattor o'g'li	
PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN.....	431
Alimardonova Gulfizoda Alimardon kizi	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA KAPITAL QO'YILMALAR HISOBINI TO'G'RI TASHKIL ETISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	434
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA KICHIK BIZNESNING IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	441
Berdimurodova Farzona Bahodir qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING BIZNES VA IQTISODIYOTDAGI ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	446
Davronova Farangiz Ilhom qizi	

ZAMONAVIY RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA PUL VA BANK TIZIMLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ISTIQBOLLARI HAMDA AHAMIYATI	452
Axtamova Ozoda Ulug'bek qizi, Cho'liyeva Gulsanam Yulchi qizi, G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTI: TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNING ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI	460
N. Qo'ziboyeva	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTINI TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLAR ORQALI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ZARURATI.....	466
Vayskulov Ramazon Alisher o'g'li	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA TURIZM KLASTERLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA IQTISODIY INTEGRATSIYA.....	470
Xushvaqto'v Ramziddin	
ILMIY SALOHİYAT VA OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINING UZVIY BOG'LIQLIGI: TAHLIL VA TAVSIYALAR	476
Muratov A'zam Alisher o'g'li, Ochilov Akram Odilovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: GREEN CREDIT.....	480
Eshtemirova Ma'rifat Akram qizi, Kabilova Shaxnoza Jurayevna	
DEHQON XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI NARXLARINING DINAMIKASI VA BOZOR MUVOZANATI MODELLARINI QO'RISH.	483
Ergashov Yashnarbek Istamovich	
The Role of Renewable Energy in the Green Economy.....	488
Khudoyberdiyeva Olima, Yakhshikulova Mokhinur	
O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish: asosiy muammolar va imkoniyatlar	494
Jumanazarov Asilbek Utkirbek o'g'li, Ulug'bek Eshmaxmatov	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING RAQOBAT USTUNLIGI ORQALI BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH OMILLARI	498
Ro'ziqulov Jamshid Ulug'bek o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH SIYOSATINING ZAMONAVIY TRENDLARI HAMDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI.....	504
Shodiyev Jahongir 504	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: O'ZBEKISTONNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	509
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna, Sh. S. Sa'dullayev	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI SOHASIDA MAHSULOTLAR INTENSIV RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH JARAYONLARI	512
Saburov Jumanazar Salievich	
SUG'URTA XIZMATLARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI VA MEXANIZMLARI.....	516
E.Sobirov	
“YASHIL IQTISODIYOT”GA O'TISH ORQALI TABIIY RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING ATROF-MUHITGA SALBIY TA'SIRINI KAMAYTIRISH	520
Xo'janova Gulshoda Otamurodovna	
QISHLOQ JOYLARDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KONSEPTUAL YO'NALISHLARI	526
Dilafuz Taylakova	
KORXONALARDA EKOLOGIK INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI TAHLILI.....	532
Ulashov Aliboy Rashid o'g'li	
YURTIMIZDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA BANK VA MOLIYAVIY TIZIMLAR UCHUN YANGI IMKONIYATLAR TAHLILI HAMDA KELGUSIDAGI ISTIQBOLLARI	538
G'aniyev Shaxzod Shuhrat o'g'li, Alarov Asilbek Oybek o'g'li	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIGI VA EKOLOGIK IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH MASALALARI.....	545
O'rinov Diyor, Xolliyev Sh.B.	

YASHIL IQTISODOYOT VA UNDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR.....	549
Ermuminov Elbek Erkin o'gli, Ilmiy rahbar: Yaxshiqulova Moxinur Toxir qizi	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA KADRLARNING TUTGAN O'RNI	553
Turayeva Nargiza Rustamovna	
IQTISODIYOTDA TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	557
G.P.Erkayeva, N.H.Qo'ziboyeva	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING AHAMIYATI VA O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH STRATEGIYASI	560
Samadova Jasmina Sherali qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
"YASHIL" ENERGETIKA VA "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT.....	564
Qarshiyeva Dilsora Ismoil qizi, Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
MAMLAKAT BUDJETINING SHAKLLANISHI VA DAROMADLAR TAQSIMOTINING IQTISODIYOTDAGI ROLI	569
Ashirqulova Sevinch Sarvar qizi, Sh. Xolliyev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	574
Urozoova Shahlo Hasan qizi, Rahmonova Tillaoy Malik qizi	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOT INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHINING KO'RSATGICHLARI.....	579
Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanakovich, Usmonov Murodjon Dusmurot o'g'li	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI TARTIBGA SOLISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	583
Mirzayev Qulmamat Djonuzoqovich, Mirzayev Azzamjon Jonuzokovich, Eshquvvatova Nodira Abdullayevna	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA IQTISODIY RESURLARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	588
Mirzayev Qulmamat Djonuzoqovich, Eshquvvatova Nodira Abdullayevna	
СТРАТЕГИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИЙ И ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОГО КАПИТАЛА В ЭПОХУ НООНОМИКИ.....	593
Чекулаева Кристина	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПРИ ПЕРЕХОДЕ К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	599
Чекулаева Кристина	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT – MAMLAKAT TARAQQIYOTINING ASOSIY OMILI.....	605
Oybek Hamdamov, Qosimov Jahongir	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA INSON KAPITALI SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA TA'LIMNING AHAMIYATI	608
M.Ostanova, Ro'ziyev Ramshid	
MODERN LEGAL BASIS FOR THE EFFICIENT USE OF FINANCIAL RESOURCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN OUR COUNTRY	613
Ismoilova Gulrux, Khayriddinov Shukhrat Botirovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SHAROITIDA TABIIY - IQTISODIY MANBAALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMI	617
Mavlonov Shaxzod Shahobiddin o'g'li, Mavlonova Surayyo Xasan qizi	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA SOHALARNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI	621
Gulrux Arslon qizi Ismoilova	

TRANSITION OF RUSSIAN REGIONS TO A CLOSED-LOOP ECONOMY

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INTRODUCTION

The circular economy (CEE) is becoming increasingly relevant in the context of global environmental and economic challenges. This model is aimed at minimizing waste and optimizing resource use, which reduces the negative impact on the environment and increases economic efficiency. The circular economy concept has gained momentum both among scholars and practitioners. However, critics claim that it means many different things to different people.¹ In Russia, which has vast natural resources but faces serious environmental problems, the transition to a CEE is a strategically important step. This essay examines the relevance of implementing a CEE in Russian regions, analyzes current initiatives, and discusses the benefits and challenges of this model.

Theoretical foundations of the circular economy

The Circular Economy (CEE), also known as the circular economy, is a concept that aims to create a sustainable production and consumption model in which materials and products are used for as long as possible and waste is minimized through recycling and reuse. The circular economy concept is much discussed in the European Union (EU), but only limited progress has been accomplished so far regarding its implementation. Most scholarly studies blame this on various technological barriers.² This model is opposed to the traditional

1 Kirchherr, J., Reike, D., & Hekkert, M. (2017). Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. *Resources, conservation and recycling*, 127, 221-232.

2 Kirchherr, J., Piscicelli, L., Bour, R., Kostense-Smit, E., Muller, J., Huibrechtse-Truijens, A., & Hekkert, M. (2018). Barriers to the circular economy: Evidence from the European Union (EU). *Ecological economics*, 150, 264-272.

linear economy based on the principle of “take-make-throw away”, which leads to the depletion of resources and the accumulation of waste.

Historical development of the concept

The ideas behind the circular economy began to take shape in the mid-20th century. In 1966, American economist and sociologist Kenneth Boulding proposed the concept of an “open economy” in his essay “The Economics of the Future Spaceship Earth.” He emphasized the need to move from a linear model of resource use to a more closed system where resources circulate repeatedly. The term “circular economy” appeared later, in the works of Western economists in the 1970s and 80s.

The USSR also developed ideas similar to the principles of the EC. In 1979, the Department of Environmental Economics was founded at the Faculty of Economics of Moscow State University, the main objective of which was to increase the resource efficiency of the economy. The Soviet Union actively introduced practices for collecting recyclable materials, such as waste paper and glass containers, which contributed to the development of elements of the circular economy. In the last few decades the Circular Economy has increasingly been advertised as an economic model that can replace the current “linear” economy whilst addressing the issues of environmental deterioration, social equity and long-term economic growth with the explicit suggestion that it can serve as a tool for Sustainable Development.³

The main principles of the circular economy include the prevention of waste through improved product design, recycling of materials and extension of the life cycle of goods. An important part of the circular economy is also the development of business models based on the rental and sharing of products. In international practice, the countries of the European Union and Japan demonstrate successful examples of the implementation of the circular economy. For example, in Germany, more than 65% of all waste is recycled, which contributes to a significant reduction in the burden on the environment.

The relevance of the transition to the EZC for Russia

Russia faces a number of environmental problems related to inefficient waste management. Every year, the country generates about 7 billion tons of waste, a significant portion of which is not recycled and is buried in landfills. Overcrowded landfills pose a threat to public health and ecosystems. For example, in the Moscow region, many landfills have already exhausted their capacity to accept new waste.

Russia’s economic dependence on the extraction and export of natural resources makes it vulnerable to fluctuations in world prices. The transition to a circular economy can contribute to the diversification of the economy through the development of new industries, such as recycling and the production of environmentally friendly goods.

Social aspects also play an important role in the relevance of the transition to a circular economy. Air and water pollution negatively affect the health of citizens, increasing health care costs. According to the World Health Organization, about 15% of all diseases in Russia are associated with unfavorable environmental conditions.

Regional initiatives and projects

The role of local authorities and businesses in the implementation of circular economy projects is extremely important. Government bodies should create favorable conditions for the development of the circular economy through legislative initiatives and financial support. The business community, in turn, can introduce innovative recycling technologies and develop new business models.

Benefits of switching to Circular Economy

The federal project “Closed Cycle Economy”, implemented within the framework of the national project “Ecology”, is designed to increase the share of waste recycling and introduce sustainable production and consumption models. This project includes the creation of a modern infrastructure for waste collection and recycling, the development of eco-technoparks and the stimulation of the use of secondary materials.

Sverdlovsk Region is one of the leaders in this area: it is actively developing the infrastructure for recycling municipal solid waste (MSW), eliminating unauthorized landfills and reclaiming contaminated areas. The region plans to recycle up to 50% of municipal waste, turning it into secondary raw materials for industry.

Other regions are also demonstrating successful results in implementing ECZ projects. For example, Moscow is actively developing a system of separate waste collection and implementing programs to reduce the use of disposable plastic packaging. St. Petersburg is implementing projects to clean up water bodies from pollution and restore ecosystems.

The circular economy (CEE) offers many benefits that cover environmental, economic and social aspects. The transition to this model allows not only to reduce the negative impact on the environment, but also to create new opportunities for business and society as a whole.

Environmental benefits:

³ Millar, N., McLaughlin, E., & Börger, T. (2019). The circular economy: swings and roundabouts?. *Ecological economics*, 158, 11-19.

Infrastructure development

Creation of recycling capacities: Construction of waste recycling and secondary materials production plants. This is especially important for industries such as construction and agriculture, where the share of secondary resources is still low.

- Development of a separate waste collection system: Implementation of waste sorting infrastructure at all levels - from households to industrial enterprises. This will increase recycling volumes and reduce the load on landfills.

Integration of technologies: Use of digital solutions such as artificial intelligence for waste sorting or blockchain for tracking secondary materials supply chains.

Environmental education of the population

Information campaigns: Conducting educational programs for the population on the importance of separate waste collection, reducing consumption and reusing things. This will help change consumer habits and increase environmental awareness.

Inclusion of the topic of the EC in educational programs: Introducing courses on sustainable development in school and higher education with an emphasis on the principles of the circular economy.

Measures to regulate supply and demand

Stimulating demand for products made from secondary materials: Introducing mandatory quotas for the use of recycled materials in construction, industry and agriculture. For example, by 2030, Russia plans to achieve 40% use of secondary resources in construction and 50% in agriculture.

Restricting the circulation of non-ecological products: Banning the use of disposable plastic packaging or introducing environmental taxes on goods with a high carbon footprint.

Innovation and technology

Developing new recycling technologies: Investing in research to create more efficient methods of recycling waste (e.g. chemical recycling of plastics).

Introducing green design: Designing products to be disassembled, repaired or recycled at the end of their useful life.

CONCLUSION

The transition of Russian regions to a closed-loop economy is a strategically important step toward achieving the sustainable development of the country. It requires a comprehensive approach, including legislative changes, investments in infrastructure, business support, and raising the environmental awareness of the population. Successful implementation of this model will not only solve the country's environmental problems but also create conditions for economic growth and improve the quality of life of citizens. The introduction of the principles of a circular economy will be the key to a sustainable future for Russia, ensuring a balance between economic development and environmental preservation for future generations.

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